

POLITICAL STRATEGIES AND ENVIRONMENTAL CHANGE: A DISCURSIVE APPROACH

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This presentation is a part of a wider investigation titled "Basic Study for Positive Action in the Neighborhood 'El Raval' through Integral Planning", carried out under request and subsidization from the Barcelona city council. In this research, different aspects about an specific neighborhood of Barcelona, named 'El Raval', were examined.

'El Raval' is a neighborhood in the old quarter of Barcelona located in the heart of the city. Apart of its historical interest, a number of relevant social problems befall in this area:

- * The population of this neighborhood is basically working class.
- * A very high population density.
- * Its particular urban structure (narrow, winding streets) and its proximity to the port have contributed to the spread of economic and social activities linked to marginal and illegal urban life, such as prostitution and drug commerce.
- * It has been a neighborhood that has received historically great waves of immigration: at first from other regions of Spain and, more recently, a migrant population from North and Central Africa. This has had a strong effect on the transformation of social relationships and the urban make up of the neighborhood as, for example, vertical Shanty towns, sub-division of living space, appearance of numerous boarding houses or sub-leasing.

Under these conditions, it is easy to understand why 'El Raval', better known as 'Barri Xino' ("China Town"), is home to one of the poorest and marginal sections of Barcelona. Due to what could be defined as 'a high level of impoverishment' and little effective attention from the Administration, 'El Raval' has become the recipient of various problems which have seriously affected its image in the eyes of the neighbors, the administration and the rest of the city.

Two elements have increased in the last few years the attention paid to the area:

- * In first place, as an effect of its location in the center of the city and the rise of housing speculation in Barcelona, this sector has become the target for many private firms whose intention it is to reconvert it into a 'residential area'.
- * In second place, coinciding with the preparations for the 1992 Olympic Games, the municipal government has started a number of programmes in an attempt to 'regenerate' the neighborhood. Fundamentally, these are based on urbanistic operations which are substantially changing the appearance of the neighborhood and which are affecting the residents in a very decisive way, most obviously apparent in the substitution of the population.

In this poster we will deal with two aspects relating to the image of this neighborhood: 'its general image' and 'the image of Governmental programmes'. This purpose was achieved through different group interviews.

PROCEDURE

67 persons were interviewed on 8 discussion groups. Three characteristics were observed in order to homogenize the make up of the groups: (a) the socioeconomic status of the participants; (b) the membership of organized groups or associations; and (c) the membership of institutional organizations at the national, regional and municipal level.

And the level of implication with the neighborhood was taken into account in order to obtain an attitudinal heterogeneity of the groups and thus provoke confrontation, increasing the discursive variability of the interviews. The methods used for the group meetings were oriented towards overcoming superficial commentary by creating a confrontation-response dynamic of opinions.

The analysis of the data can be defined, schematically, in **five phases** in order to obtain more profundity in the basis for discourse development and its forms of explanation.

1.- The first phase consists in the localization of 'topics of discourse' and 'explicative polarities'. The methodology used in this phase consists of:

- (a) an analysis of each interview in isolation in order to ascertain 'topics of discourse' and
- (b) in the gathering of an overall view for the entire corpus.

2.- In the second phase a confrontation of opinions is carried out and 'discursive web' is worked out. The procedure followed is of analyzing the group of interviews using common elements identified, and the construction of a 'discourse web' which will permit a follow up of the process of 'explaining'.

3.- Thirdly, an individual analysis of the confrontation in accordance with the 'discourse web' worked out.

4.- In fourth place the discussion of the interpretative coincidences and the establishment of common points in the various 'discursive topics'.

5.- Finally, the Conclusion and Interpretation of the whole corpus.

RESULTS

The **results** of the analysis will be presented in two parts. In first place, we develop the general image of the neighborhood differentiating between non-neighbors, neighbors, institutions and associations. In second place, the perception of the intervention planned in the city is outlined.

The Image of the Neighborhood

The **non-neighbors** relate the word 'Raval' with the expression 'Barri Xino' (legendary). This labelling appears accompanied by a whole mythology which includes prostitution, delinquency, poverty, lack of safety, etc. Their discourse on the neighborhood gravitates around three characteristics which they objectify as, poverty, drugs and delinquency, although each of the three elements are given various levels of importance depending on the relationship (usually causal) established in the group.

What seems to weigh more heavily is drugs/delinquency. This, to a large degree is the result of a kind of discourse which circulates in the neighborhood and which has given rise to the social mythology which identifies 'El Raval' as unsafe. Nevertheless, this identification does not originate in the experience of violent or unsafe situations. Actually, the most important thing in relation to the image of the neighborhood and the relationship the non-neighbors have with it, is that it is not based on experience but rather on an idea. For non-neighbors, the problem is not so much that of having been assaulted as that of feeling uncertainty (not knowing what might happen). This aspect is especially relevant as it creates a strong stigmatizing effect on the neighborhood, focusing on it all the problems which come along with urban life, and causing non-neighbors to attribute a series of characteristics to the inhabitants of the neighborhood which, occasionally, are even considered to be self evident. (Extract ¡Error! **Argumento de modificador desconocido.**)

To a great extent, this gives rise to the differentiation of us versus them, which also appears in the discourse of the neighbors (though in a different sense). This differentiation also leads to the perception of Barcelona as antagonistic towards the neighborhood. The us versus them differentiation assists in the attribution of a series of sociological and psychological characteristics to the practical totality of the inhabitants of the neighborhood. (Extract ¡Error! **Argumento de modificador desconocido.**)

For the **neighbors**, on the other hand, 'El Raval' is just another neighborhood in Barcelona. They perceive problems (drugs, delinquency, poverty) but they do not feel there is a substantial difference with those in other areas; it seems to be a difference between the objective indicators of the situation and the subjective perception of it. What they do affirm is that there is an overemphasis on the characteristics, which has led to the identification of problems, which in another context would be seen as normal, as 'The Raval Problem'. (Extract ¡Error! **Argumento de modificador desconocido.**)

The image that different social agents, especially the mass media, projects of the neighborhood has a **boomerang effect**, as it comes back, creating what the neighbors call the 'Raval sensation'. This stigma has effects on the neighborhood's social life and generates images which immediately come to mind, and in many cases produces a discourse similar to that of the non-neighbors. Frequently, this discourse circulates within the social fabric where it is amplified and exaggerated thus conditioning the relationships which are established with the neighborhood and also conditioning the administration's programmes. (Extract ¡Error! **Argumento de modificador desconocido.**)

Like the non-neighbors, the inhabitants also establish an us versus them differentiation. Although, in this case, in a different way: it is no longer a case of differentiating by using sociological and psychological characteristics, but rather between 'living in the Raval' and 'using the Raval'. Those who live in 'El Raval' define their neighborhood as a city service, a space with use value, which is taken advantage of by the residents of the entire city, like a 'duty free zone' where it is possible to satisfy 'needs' which are controlled in other neighborhoods. This value means that the neighbors consider the problems of 'El Raval' to be, not only their responsibility, but that of the entire city. Here we see how the neighbor's discourse utilizes terms of 'belonging' ('El Raval' as a part of the city), unlike the non-neighbors who use exclusive discourse (segregation and objective distancing of the neighborhood). (Extract ¡Error! **Argumento de modificador desconocido.**)

For those interviewed members of **governmental institutions**, the neighborhood is an amplified reflection of the general problems which afflict the city. The difference, they point out, is reduced to a question of magnitude. They feel 'El Raval' is the recipient of the city's problems, which the city chooses to ignore. (Extract ¡Error! **Argumento de modificador desconocido.**)

The members of **associations** deny the uniqueness of the neighborhood as assert that there are two Ravals. The neighbors also make this distinction. In fact, if we visit the neighborhood, we will observe the existence of a 'segregation' with respect to the state of urban conservation, type of population which lives there, services available, etc. Nevertheless, the discourse of the associations emphasizes, not the urban segregation, but the social segregation and the existence of problems specific to each of these two Ravals, almost speaking in terms of 'frontiers'. (Extract ¡Error! **Argumento de modificador desconocido.**)

Like the neighbors, the representatives of the associations, highlight what was described as the 'Raval sensation'. In fact, the identity of the neighborhood should not be confused with the sensation, especially when this is perceived negatively. When the interviewees speak of the 'Raval sensation' they allude to the effects that certain negative images have had and are having on their behavior and how these affect their relationships and bonds. (Extract ¡Error! **Argumento de modificador desconocido.**)

Here again the us versus them differentiation appears. In this case, 'us' being the neighbors (those which are considered real) and 'them' the immigrant population, who are largely seen to be responsible for the impoverishment of the neighborhood. (Extract ¡Error! **Argumento de modificador desconocido.**)

Image of Institutional Intervention Policy

After we have briefly seen the general image of this neighborhood, we will develop how is perceived the **intervention** planned by the city council. We will present, as we did before, the image of the intervention from different perspectives: non-neighbors, neighbors, governmental institutions and associations.

The idea **non-neighbors** have of this involvement is that, basically, it is a question of urbanistic programmes, which leave out the social dimension, and that the only objective is to improve the image. (Extract ¡Error! Argumento de modificador desconocido.)

They show concern for what they consider to be a deficient social policy. In this sense, they affirm that these programmes are not aimed at improving the quality of life of the neighbors, but rather of substituting the population through actions on the urban space. This is a recurring topic in their discourses. (Extract ¡Error! Argumento de modificador desconocido.)

They highlight the lack of social policy which takes into consideration the residents of the neighborhood. They feel it is purely an urbanistic programme. (Extract ¡Error! Argumento de modificador desconocido.)

The **neighbors** group identifies two different types of intervention: a general intervention and an urbanistic intervention. In first place, they feel that, **in general**, the programmes being implemented do not respond to any planning. They perceive a disassociation of different actions and interpret this to mean that the administration only aspires to diminish the various problems, but not to solve them. Thus they state it is an image campaign. (Extract ¡Error! Argumento de modificador desconocido.)

On the other hand, they highlight the little attention the City Council gives their demands. They feel the actions are other than those needed by the neighbors. Thus, they see these actions as taking place **in** the neighborhood but not **for** the neighborhood. They feel the administration shows concern for the neighborhood's problems publically only in order to gain political respectability, instead of working on the problems that grip the community. (Extract ¡Error! Argumento de modificador desconocido.)

In second place, concerned with the **urbanistic intervention**, the most generalized discourse in this area is the generation of uncertainty. All the neighbors agree that a lack of information exists, which provokes a state of defenselessness, which in turn manifests itself as general abandon and disorientation. (Extract ¡Error! Argumento de modificador desconocido.)

This uncertainty is more obvious when the neighbors ask themselves what will happen to those affected by the demolition of old buildings. The perception of action in but not for the neighborhood is interpreted in terms of substitution of the population, which they feel is motivated by an attempt to increase land values in the area and thus obtain a better image before the 1992 Olympic Games (we must not forget that this neighborhood is located in the center of Barcelona). (Extract ¡Error! Argumento de modificador desconocido.)

In the case of the members of **governmental institutions**, the representatives assert the need for a high level of commitment in order to face their daily tasks and a great capacity of adaptation to the

'modus vivendi' of the neighborhood in order to tackle the problems they face on the job. (Extract ¡Error! Argumento de modificador desconocido.)

They feel their work is affected by the labelling to which the neighborhood is subject (stigmatization, 'Raval sensation') and the lack of specific plans of action, while at the same time recognizing the shortage of resources which limit their capacity to act. One of the aspects they point out as top priority, in terms of programmes, is sanitation. In fact, the neighborhood has a substantial sanitation problem, apparent from the high infant mortality rate and notable percentage of residents with tuberculosis.

With respect to the urbanistic programmes, they agree with the neighbors that this is the greatest problem, and with social consequences which have yet to be calculated. Their intervention has been centered on the human problem which was generated by the closing down of boarding houses (main residence for a large part of the population). Nevertheless there is much consensus on the fact that the institutions only respond to demands and not necessities, which in 'El Raval' is not acceptable. (Extract ¡Error! Argumento de modificador desconocido.)

According to the **members of associations**, the programmes being carried out currently are essentially urbanistic. The crucial point of these is not the changing of the appearance of the neighborhood, but the effects this is having on the neighbors. Their opinion is that the programmes have been designed without taking into account the neighbors. They consider these actions to be motivated by political interest and that they do not take on the social problems that exist and that they are creating. They affirm that the final target of these programmes is to give a good impression of Barcelona in 1992 (Extract ¡Error! Argumento de modificador desconocido.)

Their opinion is that these programmes have been put in effect **not in order to improve** the living conditions, **but to adapt it** to Barcelona's necessities in the short and medium term, and for this reason they feel there is a process of substitution of the population. (Extract ¡Error! Argumento de modificador desconocido.)

CONCLUSIONS

After analysis of the data, we can extract a series of effects which show up and characterize the discourse on the neighborhood 'El Raval'.

Firstly, we can observe how certain problems in the neighborhood are focused. In fact, the discourse which circulates in the neighborhood, isolates a series of characteristics which are exaggerated and become the complete image of the neighborhood. These characteristics are, at the same time, fed by the social mythology constructed in the past which conforms to a naturalized discourse.

This focus follows a process which, taken to its ultimate conclusion, leads to the labelling and objectivization of certain characteristics and causes partial aspects to become the totality of the problem (object, neighborhood) and the problem to become self evident.

The constructed evidence, circulates throughout the social fabric generating new images which feed the already existing mythology, and is subject to an amplification process which deforms, even more if possible, the original image. Finally, this amplified discourse becomes shared by all the social actors (neighbors, non-neighbors, governmental institutions and associations) which has its effect on the relationships they maintain while conditioning governmental assistance, as a deformed image is objectified, naturalized and transformed into evident.

On the other hand, this deformed image provokes what the neighbors have called the 'Raval sensation' and is no more than the introjection and assumption of this discourse and images which gives rise to specific behaviors, relationships, and actions.

With respect to relationships, we see that they are conditioned by statements using exclusive terms: us versus them, which has different meanings depending on whether one belongs to the neighborhood or not. Here we have the differentiation of the neighbors between 'real neighbors' (under the criteria of length of residence) and 'others' which normally identifies the immigrant population from North and Central Africa, who are blamed for much of the neighborhood's ills. With respect to non-neighbors, the relationship is also exclusive and in discourse is stated as the antagonism us versus neighbors (to whom they attribute a series of, almost naturalized, psychological and sociological characteristics), and city versus neighbors (in many cases the municipal administration personified).

On the other hand, as becomes clear in the interviews, the basic characteristic of the relationship with the neighborhood, is not the fact of having experienced conflictive situations there, but the idea that these can occur. The extreme manifestation of this polarity is characterized by the uncertainty demonstrated with respect to the neighborhood.

The manifestation of this uncertainty is reflected by the overemphasis of the neighborhood's characteristics (characteristics which in other neighborhoods are accepted and normalized) which causes that discourse on the problems of 'El Raval' ends up being on 'El Raval' as a problem.

This is not harmless as it decisively conditions the relationship the neighbors establish with their neighborhood and the governmental programmes which are implemented.

Thus, as we have attempted to show, the programmes carried out by the administration are seen and experienced as incoherent or, in some cases, even as attacks on the neighborhood and its residents. This is the understanding the inhabitants of 'El Raval' have of the programmes. It is important to note that the neighbors do not manifest an attitude of rejection of the intervention (actually, they feel it is essential) but rather against its effects. Basically, they are seen as urbanistic, without previous planning and with a high cost in social terms. So, they transmit a discourse on government intervention in which the main argument is constructed around the substitution of population in which only the survival of the neighborhood will be achieved, but without its present inhabitants: a neighborhood which be conserved, cleaned, improved but with different neighbors.

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EXTRACTS FROM THE DISCUSSION GROUPS

OVERALL IMAGE

¡Error! Argumento de modificador desconocido. Non-Neighbors; Medium Socioeconomic Status.

- But, there's a problem... the streets aren't save, you never know what you'll find behind the door, well it can all be very pretty but... it doesn't help me go there.

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- It's that I don't dare. I feel alone, that is, out of place, I don't know how they will be. And well, there are a lot of immigrants too, aren't there? I think, it seems to me, that well as they don't have economic means they are capable of things, as I would be capable of a lot of things if I didn't have any, would I?

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- ... and he said to me, but it's not the first opinion which is a little (...) that who's fault is it if one lives in 'el Raval'. I answered him: 'You know what? I thought you were smarter'. It's not a question of who's fault it is if you live in 'el Raval'. This questions, that those of us who life in 'el Raval' and have decent jobs and pay taxes, should have the same services as they do in other places.

¡Error! Argumento de modificador desconocido. Neighbors; Low socioeconomic status.

- Yes, I think that these people,.. of course, the neighborhood is obviously in bad condition, but these people think it's a lot worse than it is.

¡Error! Argumento de modificador desconocido. Neighbors; Low socioeconomic status.

- Everyone who comes here feel they have a right to do anything, the right to do anything. Starting whit the municipal services that come here and treat things any which way.

¡Error! Argumento de modificador desconocido. Public Institutions Working in the Neighborhood.

- Well, I think all the neighborhood in Barcelona have problems with old people. With old people who are living there alone, problems with people who are unemployed and don't have jobs, etc. and the vagabonds, even Sarria [upper class neighborhood] has vagabonds. What I mean is, up to now we've been talked a little about the populations that are inherent in a big city, that is, not only in 'el Raval'.
- Yes, but 'el Raval' might be.
- We've talked about 'el Raval' but want it to be clear, I say this because we've had experiences and we've compared them to other neighborhoods and, yes, well, I guess there is more, but all the other neighborhoods all these problems exist, the vagabonds, the old people who are sick, oab...
- Yes, I think so. Maybe I'm wrong but I feel that 'el Raval' maybe it's true but there are differences. First, there are a lot more people, and then, that's very important to me, and I've lived through it, the attitude of the people in the neighborhood in these cases, that is, the city is overflowing, and 'el Raval' today...

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- THIS IS INCREDIBLY INTERESTING, BECAUSE THE IMAGE WE HAVE OF THE NEIGHBORHOOD IS THAT THERE IS A POPULATION...
- 'el Raval' is two Ravals, and to me, it's not one but two, I've no doubt, this is, it's like this. There is South Raval and North Raval. North Raval just another neighborhood, ~~pele~~ live there, its more neighborly. South Raval though is just a stop over neighborhood.

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- It's true, and we ourselves are realizing it. About 5 years ago or three years ago, not very long, eh? There were... we perceived ourselves, from within the Tenants Association that, the neighborhood was in decay. At last North Raval was decaying, the 'Raval sensation' was eating it, the sensation that, that, its a lost neighborhood, best to get out as soon as possible.

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- Yes, well, what happens is that.. the worse things in the neighborhood don't belong to the neighborhood. 90% of it comes from outside the neighborhood, the drug dealers, there are a few but, the percentage is much higher, I believe, of those from outside of the neighborhood. Here ~~there~~ is known because it has always, from Conde Street... south of Nou de la Rambla Street where now they've torn down almost everything and it's all new, that's always been the 'Barri Xino'.
- The border of the 'Barri Xino' has always been Nou Street..Nou Street was the border. Now that neighborhood has decayed, well, because of all these foreigners, but the neighbors, us... we live here, we're a little afraid at night, during the day we live normally, but at night everyone's afraid to go out, even though I spend hours on the balcony or at the window and I never hear anything, sometimes there are fights between... all these people, between themselves, but oh yes.

IMAGE OF INSTITUTIONAL INTERVENTION POLICY

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Socioeconomic Status.

- It's a policy for an audience.
- For who?
- An audience.
- Yes.
- A policy for an audience.

Non-Neighbors; Medium Socioeconomic Status.

- The information I get is for the district, the old quarter, put all their energies directed at urbanistic modifications.
- Yes, with urbanism, what I know of, too, is all the urban real estate.

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Socioeconomic Status.

- What happens is that 'el Raval' is located, let's say, in the most authentic part of Barcelona and that's why they want to clean it up. But, socially I think it's very selfish, its only to look nice.

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Socioeconomic Status.

- And I think what's being done is purely urbanistic.
- WHY AREN'T THEY DOING ANYTHING ON A SOCIAL LEVEL?
- I don't...
- I believe, at least before, that it was of course you see what you see on television and they said that a lot of people were starving and nobody was doing anything... there was even a place, I don't know who ran it, they gave our food.

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- WHAT IS THE CITY COUNCIL DOING WITH THE NEIGHBORHOOD?
- Nothing.
- Nothing, absolutely nothing.
- YOU'RE VERY EMPHATIC. DO YOU ALL FEEL THE SAME?
- Yes.
- THE CITY COUNCIL DOES NOTHING?
- Very little.
- NOT ONLY IN QUESTIONS OF DRUGS, OR AS YOU COMMENTED DELINQUENCY ETC. BUT ON A GENERAL LEVEL, NEIGHBORHOOD SERVICES, ETC. WHAT WE COULD CALL THE QUALITY OF LIFE IN THE NEIGHBORHOOD.
- They talk and talk. But you don't see any results. ~~At~~the moment you can't see any results.
- The only good thing they do are the subsidies mentioned before. They said there are 50 or 60 children who are subsidized. But, they have a hard time, because the subsidies don't arrive on time and there's nothing to spare, and often they have to ask other sectors for help.
- SO THERE IS ONLY A SUBSIDIES POLICY?
- On the institutional level, practically nothing.
- They do other things, they try to reeducate the prostitutes.
- Oh, yes.
- They give them courses from, I don't know if its the Employment Services or who.

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- I think its awful, that is, for a time, the only thing the Administration did ~~was~~ fill the neighborhood with police, close down bars, and somehow cause more insecurity than what they were trying to get rid of in the first place. If a neighborhood has bars, there's movement, there are people. It's a safe area, at least to me. You ~~start~~ closing down the bars, the areas become deserted and that can make them unsafe. And on the other hand, this campaign to improve the neighborhood, well, with the opening of the Museum beside the Charity House or the creation of infrastructure, etc. ~~sees~~ like a classic cleaning project, I think they're things the people can't take advantage of, and they raise land values and the people have to go live somewhere else. The rents increase, because the Government has spent money on building Plazas, these ~~flts~~ flats that were affordable, aren't any more, so it's an improvement the neighbors won't enjoy.

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- But, what do we know? We don't know anything.
- Yes, it's that they keep changing it. You can see they are preparing projects and then when the time comes, when... because of course, there are a lot of families here to locate. It's what we talked about.
- It's shameful with the doctors there are, technicians, engineers and all that, and that we still don't know, after so many years of rumors, we don't know how much time we have left, in the neighborhood. Which of us is affected by the... and its shameful it isn't know. That something I do complain about.

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Socioeconomic Status

- I don't believe it's appropriate, not possible nor appropriate, but in fact what's being done cleaning up the neighborhood, that is moving all the drug dealer to San Cosme, in Prat. Well, I guess they want an neighborly image for 1992 and all that so their taking measure: police. I don't know if they're taking social measures or not.
- YOU DONT SEE THEM
- No, no, because the same level of social decay there was two years ago, you still see today.

Neighbors: Medium Socioeconomic Status

- But that's no more than the buildings they've been tearing down, people from the neighborhood and they have been displaced...
- That, indeed, is the problem.
- I suppose they must feel very, very (...) where they've taken them.
- Of course, they have no right.
- That is, even though they have been given housing because it was said that the City Council would build housing for the people who were moved out. That they wouldn't give them the 200 square meter flat, but if there were 3 people they would give them a smaller place, but they would leave them in the neighborhood.
- In condition.
- And that's not what happened.
- It hasn't happened.
- No, it hasn't happened. They've kicked them out and they've been left with nothing.
- On Floristas de las Ramblas Street they kicked out 8 families.
- Change of neighborhood.
- And none of them are here. They all had to leave.
- And these people were normal people.
- Yes, they were normal people. They weren't delinquents or (...). And they've had to leave. They've left. Those who had money have chosen a flat more or less where they could. If they couldn't and the Government has had to take, are living in Besos, or la Verdeda or one of those places. But of course, it's completely...

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- No, but it's that, it's absolutely... We comment on it a lot. That is, I live in a neighborhood that would be called... I get on the Metro in a neighborhood with gardens etc. I get on the metro and get off at Drassanes, but at that metro station I have changed my 'clip', and I arrive at the Hospital and my language changes. I don't know... sometimes we talk... we especially get a lot of transvestites because they get a lot of kidney trouble etc..., and I'm talking to 'la Paloma', with the John, and sometimes I think: 'Oh my god, if my mother saw me' And they come... this is what the whore's say, others from the neighborhood that tell you that their life story, that their pimp is at home and that they keeping him 'cirrotico' and all that. And a drug addict comes and you chat with him and try to solve something and give him a center where they will give him methadone. You act as a kind of chameleon and I suppose that social workers do the same. When you deal with an old lady you talk one way, and then, when a drug addict whose trying to fool you, you see that too. Because sometimes, well... there are a lot of people who are users... who are resourceful. Right? They're try to get what they can from you.

¡Error! Argumento de modificador desconocido. Public Institutions Working in the Neighborhood.

- No, no, this issue is never ending, almost. That is, the closing of the Boarding Houses is a large scale issue. Oh... it's affected.
- EXCUSE ME FOR INTRUDING ON THE TOPIC, HOW MANY PEOPLE DID YOU SAY LIVED IN THE BOARDING HOUSE?
- I think 40.
- AND HOW MANY OF THEM HAVE FOUND SOLUTIONS?
- Well, I wouldn't know. It's...
- AND WHAT HAPPENS TO THOSE WHO HAVE NO SOLUTION?
- They do what they can.
- They move somewhere else... it's that sometimes it's this... you have to reconcile what.. first, I understand that a situation is provoked which the person has never thought of. For example, for these people, I talking of the Boarding house closed on Nou de la Rambla, okay? These people grew up, grew old, their live was set, they were very comfortable in the neighborhood and they had contacts in the neighborhood and that was their surroundings. Then, you can't think of moving. Then they suggested to some that they move into retirement homes, which they had never thought of, and they talked it over with their families. Well, in each case, an attempt is made, now... sometimes the people move.

¡Error! Argumento de modificador desconocido. Members of Socioeconomic Associations in the Neighborhood

- ... I want to go on with the issue of the media. It's super important, because I suppose you've chosen the old quarter for a reason, for something... I don't know, also... whether you want to or not... whether you want to or not, you have to talk about the problems because obviously, in some ways, you can't live on these streets, even if you want to. That is, it's real, that is... you understand? Then there is also a political interest, obviously, that is, there is a political interest because, that is for all of, the whole 1992 thing. That is, for the last four years the politicians are trying, from the City Council, the regional Generalitat, they try more, I don't know, it doesn't matter, from all levels they are trying to make this place less chaotic, that it would be an embarrassment, when the people came for a visit in 1992, to the Olympic Games and all that. There is some interest, actually the municipal government has made, is making a... an investment and so is the regional government, the Welfare Office and all are making investments.

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- I don't know. That is to say, to be again, and I'm very stubborn! mean, the neighborhood I think is saved, that is, obviously the neighborhood will live, tons of people will come, that's for sure, because that clear, just with the Charity house installations you don't need anything else and the lower Parallel they just have to water it a bit, and obviously, the neighborhood is saved, but the people in the neighborhood is what's in danger, not the neighborhood... has now, living downtown has become fashionable, maybe because there are not a lot of other fashionable, ~~why~~ because there are not a lot of other places to go, it still has only been rehabilitated a bit, but I don't know, anything of what we're discussing now.